

Devonian ophiolites of the Variscan Belt and their controversial origin: From the decease of the Rheic Ocean to the birth of an intracontinental pull-apart basin.

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Abstract

The suture zone depicted by the Variscan Belt includes several ophiolites of which the most frequent have reported ages at c. 395-400 Ma. Three of these ophiolites have been described at the Allochthonous Complexes from NW Spain: Careon, Purrido and Moeche ophiolites. They are mainly constituted by mafic rock types (greenschists, amphibolites, varied metagabbros and diabase dikes) and ultramafics, with no clear evidence of presence of metavolcanics and scarce sediments. Only the Careon ophiolite shows an identifiable original sequence where the relationships between the different rock types can be observed and it does not correspond to a classical Penrose-type structural architecture, reason why it was initially interpreted as supra-subduction type ophiolite. Considered as representative of the closure stages of the Rheic Ocean their origin and interpretation has changed with the studies of the geochemical features of their mafic lithologies. Their whole rock geochemistry varies from island-arc tholeiitic to N-MORB types supporting the initial hypothesis of a supra-subduction origin that was linked to the development of new oceanic crust at an intra-ocenic subduction zone responsible of the closure of the Rheic Ocean. Further studies of zircon geochemistry in the different units revealed the presence of a Mesoproterozoic zircon population and epsilon Hf signatures which pointed to participation of older crustal components in the origin of this Devonian oceanic crust. These data led to the proposal of a new interpretation suggesting that this oceanic basin originated in a pull-apart setting developed after a first collision between Gondwana and Laurussia supercontinents. In order to achieve a most precise model it is time to display the whole set of geochemical data together and establishing in future work a comparison with equivalent Devonian ophiolites located along

Europe in Cornwall, Armorican Massif and Bohemian Massif (Lizard, Drain and Sleza ophiolites respectively).